

TECHNOLOGY FOR OBTAINING NATURAL MELON JAM

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ABSTRACT

С целью изучения последних достижений учёных, ведущих исследования по данной тематике авторами был проведён обзор некоторых зарубежных статей, посвящённых переработке плодов дыни. В статье приводятся некоторые сведения о переработке дыни и технология получения натурального дынного джема. Приведены основные характеристики сортов дыни выращенные в Республике Каракалпакстане.

Melons, being the most ancient culture of Uzbekistan, have come a long way of their transformation and development. Being bred, initially from wild forms, as they got into the conditions of cultivated agriculture, the nature of melons gradually changed. Mankind purposefully created new, more valuable varieties. For many centuries, folk breeders from generation to generation have continuously selected the best fruits of melons with high palatability, gradually grafted and consolidated these traits by inheritance. With their painstaking work, they created varieties of melons that have survived to this day, which have no equal in other countries.

The history of growing melons on the territory of modern Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan dates back more than one hundred years. This is evidenced by both written sources (Abu Ali Ibn Sino, Beruniy, the Moroccan traveler Ibn Botut, our compatriot Bobur, etc.), and archaeological excavations. An example of this is the seeds

of cultivars of this truly wonderful plant, found during excavations of the settlement of Topyrak-kala (I-IV century AD). It is known for certain that melons were exported by camel caravans already in those distant times to China, India, Iran and Egypt.

To date, more than 160 varieties of melons are grown in Uzbekistan, which are exported to neighboring countries, to Russia and even to Europe and enchant the inhabitants of these countries with their honey aroma and unsurpassed taste.

New varieties of melons were bred by selective selection and crossing. With repeated repetition of this approach, the sugar content, flavor and keeping quality gradually increased. For example, in the Khorezm oasis and the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the most keeping varieties have been created.

Local native varieties, well adapted to certain soil and climatic conditions, when transferred to other areas with other

soil and climatic conditions, lose their taste qualities, and yields decrease. Only certain varieties retain their valuable qualities when grown in other conditions.

Melon jam is boiled to a thick jelly-like state of crushed melon pulp with sugar. For the production of natural jam, fresh pulp of summer-autumn melons with a hard, crisp texture and high sugar content is used.

The gelling ability of melon pulp, from which jam or jam is made, is judged by a clot test. To do this, squeeze out 10-50 cm³ of juice and add 15-30 cm³ of ethyl alcohol to it. This forms a clot. If the clot is dense, filamentous, not strayed into a lump, then there is not enough natural pectin in the raw material. In this case, citrus pectin or pectin concentrate from quince fruits, apples, plums and currants is added during the jam brewing process. As a last resort, fresh melon peel, chopped on a blender, is used. It is rich in pectin substances and contains in its composition up to 6% by absolutely dry weight.

When preparing raw materials, high-sugar melon varieties are selected, preferably with red pulp: Ich-kzyl Uzbek, Ich-kzyl Turkmen, or with white pulp: Ak-kaun, Kokcha. Arbakeshka, with firm crispy flesh. The fruits received for processing are washed, peeled and the testes with placentas are removed. Prepared melon pulp is crushed on a homogenizer and blanched to improve gelling and inactivate enzymes. In this case, protopectin passes

into a soluble form of pectin. The raw materials are blanched in a double-slit steam boiler with a frame stirrer at a temperature of 100°C under vacuum.

After blanching, the melon pulp is boiled down to a thick viscous state, and at the end of cooking, the prepared gelling solution from natural food pectin and citric acid is added for 10-15 minutes. The product is boiled down to a solids content of 69-73% and hot poured into glassware with a capacity of 0.25-0.5 dm³.

To improve the quality of jam and give it a natural melon aroma and taste, during cooking, the evaporated juice vapor with aromatic substances is sent to a condenser and captured in the form of a distillate. Upon completion of the jam cooking, the aromatic distillate is poured into the jam and thoroughly mixed with the stirrer turned on.

In the same apparatus, you can cook melon confiture, which is the same jam, but flour with pectin substances, made from the peel of melons, is added to the mass during cooking.

Prepared blanched melon pulp is boiled to a solids content of 57-58%. At the end of cooking, solutions of pectin, citric acid, vanillin (1.5 g per 100 kg), 0.06% sorbic acid in the form of a 10% solution prepared on hot t=85°C melon honey with a concentration of 70% are added to the product.

The finished product is poured into glass jars 0.25-0.5 dm³.

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